

FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ENTERPRISE AND EFFICIENCY OF ITS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. In the conditions of development of market relations, the financial stability of an enterprise as an object of management acquires particular relevance. Based on the current economic conditions, the study of the process of ensuring the financial stability of an enterprise requires an integrated approach to the study, the development of a conceptual framework for managing it as a set of theoretical and methodological provisions that are currently not sufficiently studied in depth. This paper formulates the main conceptual provisions, principles, and functions of managing the financial stability of an enterprise in the context of integration processes in a market environment.

Keywords: financial stability, concept, management, financial security.

INTRODUCTION

The tasks of modern development of Russian companies related to the constant overcoming of crisis situations determine special requirements for financial stability as a strategic factor in the financial security of the company's activities, the growth of its business activity and investment attractiveness. In the context of globalization of the economic space, the problem of managing the financial stability of a company acquires particular relevance. Solving this problem urgently requires improving the concept of managing the financial stability of a company, since it has a direct impact on the effectiveness of such management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Managing the financial stability of an enterprise is one of the most important economic problems in modern conditions, since insufficient financial stability can lead to the insolvency of the enterprise and the lack of funds for the development of production, and excess will hinder development, burdening costs enterprises with excess inventories and reserves.

The complexity of the process of ensuring the financial stability of a company determines the complexity and ambiguity of the interpretation of the concept of "financial stability". O.V. Vishnevskaya considers financial stability as "the objective financial condition of an enterprise when its own funds exceed non-

current assets, inventories and costs” [3, p. 4]. The above definition reflects only one of the states of financial stability - absolute stability, in which the enterprise is not threatened by the loss of financial independence, and financial risk is minimal. Domestic economists S.M. Bukhonova, Yu.A. Doroshenko, O.B. Benderskaya understands financial stability as “the ability of an enterprise to maintain a normal financial condition under the adverse influences of internal and external environmental factors due to the optimal structure of capital and assets, the optimal ratio between assets and the sources of their formation, and the effective use of all types of resources and rational reinvestment policy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study of financial sustainability from the perspective of a systems approach allows us to define it as a state formed by a set of financial resources at various levels of social production. From the author’s point of view, the financial stability of an enterprise is a holistic set of financial resources, adequate to a certain level of systemic interactions of financial flows, taking into account their complex combinations at a certain level, necessary and sufficient to obtain income from capital gains of an economic entity.

One of the essential features of the financial stability of an enterprise is temporality, which is due to the continuous, sustainable movement of financial flows in time and space. The relevance of the time aspect in determining the financial stability of an enterprise is especially obvious during a period of high inflation rates. Stabilization of the level of financial stability of an enterprise is possible only in conditions of expanded reproduction of the company’s capital, which has the property of enhancing effects: when the value of the investment object increases, there is an interference of internal (internal) and external (external) effects, which, in turn, in turn, manifests itself in a qualitative change in economic relations and the structure of needs of society as a whole. In this case, the end user is not the actor, but the entire economic system of social production. Therefore, when managing the financial stability of an enterprise, it is necessary to rationally combine the interests of economic entities, credit and banking organizations as the main suppliers of financial resources, and the state, which implements methods of influencing its financial stability in the mode of combining market self-regulation and state-public regulation through taxation.

Based on the theoretical premises stated above, the concept of managing the financial stability of an enterprise in the context of strengthening integration processes in the market environment should be based on the following provisions:

1. The multiplier effect of the achieved results of the enterprise is enhanced, which, in turn, manifests itself in the strengthening of the effect of financial leverage, a qualitative change in financial relations and the structure of the enterprise's sources of financing.

2. The set of elements of the financial stability management system of an enterprise and its nature do not depend on the socio-economic formation, therefore, a unified methodology can be used to study financial stability at all stages of the historical development of the economic system. However, the structure of the elements of the enterprise's financial stability management system is determined by the level of development of the group of integrating factors. This group of factors includes organizational, institutional and information factors and determines the connection between the enterprise and the credit, banking, tax spheres, state and municipal finance and other economic entities by general financial relations regarding accumulation and distribution financial resources, socially integrating them through institutions, organization and information. Consequently, the structure of the elements of the enterprise's financial stability management system is dynamic and changes over time under the influence of objective preconditions - the emergence of a need among economic entities for the innovative development of the enterprise, which manifests itself in new financial needs and determines the search for new sources and forms financing.

3. The financial environment affects the financial stability of the enterprise, and the latter, in turn, affects the complex of mutual multilateral business relations of the enterprise with the subjects of financial relations, the quantitative and qualitative composition of financial resources. On the one hand, enterprises, due to the strong influence of exogenous factors that impede the growth of financial results, are experiencing an acute shortage of financial resources; on the other hand, due to the shortage of financial resources, an external environment is developing that is extremely unfavorable for increasing financial stability, which causes a deterioration in the financial condition of individual business entities. The level of financial stability of an enterprise is largely determined by the processes occurring in the external environment, and the accumulation of financially stable enterprises ensures the openness of the economic system, which is capable of not only reinvesting its own funds, but also attracting external financial flows, which ultimately creates conditions for sustainable economic growth.

An enterprise is a system that is in constant interaction with the external environment through the exchange of funds and other assets received from or spent on investments, access to information about fluctuations in securities prices, etc. In this case, making financial decisions in the field of managing its financial stability should be based on the following principles:

- *integration of assessment* of the results of the influence of external and internal factors and communication channels that form the expectations of stakeholders.

- *variability of key factors* influencing the financial stability of the enterprise. The effectiveness of managing the financial stability of a company is the result of the interaction of key factors that reflect the main directions of the enterprise's activities;

- *balance of results*. The interrelation of financial stability factors determines the need to balance them in terms of placement and attraction of financial resources, building management of the financial stability of the enterprise as a unified system, which, in turn, is a subsystem of the company's financial management

CONCLUSION

Thus, the increasing influence of expectations or prospects for business development on financial results, increasing the sensitivity of business to changes in the external environment due to the globalization of the economic space necessitate the need to take into account the complex of proposed theoretical provisions for managing the financial stability of an enterprise in its practical activities, which will ensure: firstly, a comprehensive assessment of the financial stability of the enterprise, which consists in the unity and interrelation of a number of key indicators characterizing the activities of the enterprise; secondly, analysis of cause-and-effect dependencies between indicators measuring the financial results of activities and those internal (production) factors that led to these results; thirdly, planning the activities of the enterprise taking into account the achieved results, as well as determining quantitative criteria for predicting the threshold values of its sustainable financial development and including them in the financial planning system.

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